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What Drives Teaching Performance at School? The Determinants of School Teacher Performance

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the factors that affect teacher performance with organizational commitment as a mediation between professional commitment and job satisfaction to teacher performance. In the realization of the achievement of target student scores based on the results of the National Examination for the 2016/2017 academic year to 2018/2019 academic year for the Djakarta Christian Schools Association in South Jakarta. The problem has been identified that the lack of attention from the school is an impact on teacher performance. The unilateral policies given to the teacher have become tiring pressure on the teacher and have an impact on the lack of desire for creativity in improving student learning outcomes as seen in the results of students' final exam scores. This study uses Professional Commitment and Job Satisfaction as independent variables, Teacher Performance as the dependent variable, and Organizational Commitment as a moderating variable. This study used 29 teachers as respondents and used SPSS software in processing and analyzing data. This research results that Job Satisfaction affects Organizational Commitment, Job Satisfaction affects Teacher Performance, Organizational Commitment affects Teacher Performance, Professional Commitment affects Organizational Commitment and Professional Commitment affects Teacher Performance. Job Satisfaction indirectly affects Teacher Performance through Organizational Commitment, and Professional Commitment indirectly affects Teacher Performance through Organizational Commitment.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, Professional Commitment, Teacher Performance

1. Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Teacher performance has certain specifications. Teacher performance can be seen and measured based on the specifications or competency criteria that each teacher must have. With regard to teacher performance, the form of behavior in question is the teacher's activities in the learning process. With regard to teacher performance standards in the guide book for teacher performance appraisal by supervisors, it is explained that teacher performance standards are related to the quality of teachers in carrying out their duties such as working with

students individually, preparing and planning lessons, utilizing learning media, involving students in various learning experiences, and leadership active teachers (Kusmianto, 1997). Teacher performance is real behavior displayed by teachers as work performance based on established standards and in accordance with their role (related to the role of teachers in the learning process) in school (Rivai, 2009). Teacher performance can also be defined as the implementation of the learning process both in class and outside the classroom in addition to other activities, such as working on school administration and learning administration, carrying out guidance and services to students, and carrying out assessments (Rusyan, 2001). So it can be concluded, what is meant by teacher performance is the extent to which a teacher works in accordance with existing procedures in achieving the goals that have been planned. Measurement indicators are leadership, class mastery, quality information and planning, use of human resources, assurance of product and service quality, quality of results and student satisfaction.

The Djakarta Christian Schools Association (DCSA), is a school that has been established since 1942. The existence of this school is spread across West Java (Depok Area) and in Jakarta there are several locations. The research this time was conducted at one of the DCSAs in the South Jakarta area, to be precise, at Kebayoran Baru District. DCSA is a school that is a source of pride and a barometer of assessment of other schools. With a fairly complete variety of extracurricular activities, strategic location, the number of hours for English subjects is more than other DCSA schools and each batch only provides one class. However, seen from the instability of the National Exam (NE) scores, it has even tended to decline for 3 years (2017-2019) for the two levels in the Kebayoran Baru district's DCSA (Junior and Senior High School). The decline in the quality of the test results is influenced by professional commitment, job satisfaction and organizational policies or the policy provider concern for teachers. Teacher performance is expected to be improved along with the increasing level of Organizational Commitment by teachers. There is a change in policy by being willing to listen to some of the complaints or teacher input is expected to improve teacher performance.

Factors that affect teacher performance from the internal side in learning activities are seen from the level of teacher education, teaching supervision, upgrading programs, a conducive climate, facilities and infrastructure, physical and mental conditions of teachers, leadership styles of principals, welfare assurance, managerial abilities school and others. Meanwhile, the factors that influence teacher performance from the external side are Professional Commitment, Organizational Commitment, Organizational Commitment, and Job Satisfaction.

Professional Commitment refers to the strength of an individual's identification with the profession. Individuals with high professional commitment are characterized as having high trust and acceptance of professional goals, a desire to try their best on behalf of the profession and a strong desire to maintain their membership in the profession (Mowday *et al*, 1979 in Rahayu & Faisal, 2005). Then job satisfaction is one of the factors that affect work performance because that ultimately affects organizational effectiveness. And also employee job satisfaction is not enough to only be given incentives, but employees also need motivation, recognition from their superiors for their work, a work situation that is not monotonous and there are opportunities to take initiative and be creative. Meanwhile, the organizational commitment factor can be identified into four factors. First, student learning and school development, second, demand for school teaching and practice, third, teaching as a career choice, fourth, teacher-student attitude interactions. The results of these studies indicate that the factors of teaching as a career have an influence on teaching commitment. Followed by student learning and school development. Student teacher interaction factors, as well as teaching demand factors and school practices contribute to increasing teacher teaching commitment (Rots *et al.*, 2010).

1.2 Prior Studies

There are several previous studies, one of which is research by Surbakti (2019), which states that teacher commitment to school has a positive effect on job satisfaction. Then Ningsih (2019) which states that commitment, competence and work environment together have a significant and significant effect on teacher performance. In addition, Kusumaningtyas (2019) states that there is a relationship between organizational commitment, work discipline and the quality of work life on teacher performance. It can be interpreted that organizational commitment, work discipline, and quality of work life can be used as predictors to predict teacher performance. Then the research by Nongkeng, *et al* (2012) which results indicates that by assessing student learning outcomes

by lecturers, this is the basis for giving rewards to lecturers from university leaders. And also research by Panjaitan (2012) which states that the creation of good work motivation and work commitment can encourage school quality improvement. This will lead to openness to the deficiencies or weaknesses faced by teachers that previously will be resolved, so that they will contribute to improving them in the future, which will make all elements of company personnel work properly as expected. And Kaliri (2008) which states that work discipline, work motivation have a significant effect on performance.

1.3 Hypothesis Development

The existence of a commitment to a vocation in accordance with the profession that is taken (in this research, the profession as a teacher) fosters a feeling of belonging to a teaching place and wants to provide the best for the school where it teaches. Professional commitment is related to the level of individual loyalty to the profession, such as perceptions by that individual (Trisaningsih, 2003).

H₁ = There is a significant direct influence between professional commitment to organizational commitment. Job satisfaction is the level of individual satisfaction with their position in the organization relative to other colleagues. There is satisfaction in terms of comfort at work, from the income earned, sufficient to fulfill their life, foster a sense of belonging to the organization where they work. Meanwhile, Organizational Commitment is related to the level of individual loyalty as part of the organization. This is reflected in the individual's attitude towards the organization.

H₂ = There is a significant direct effect between Job Satisfaction on Organizational Commitment. There is a relationship between organizational commitment, work discipline and the quality of work life on teacher performance. It can be interpreted that organizational commitment, work discipline, and quality of work life can be used as predictors to predict teacher performance. From the results of this study, it can be seen that there is a direct positive relationship between organizational commitment and teacher performance.

H₃ = There is a significant direct influence between Organizational Commitment to Teacher Performance. Teacher commitment to the organization shows that teachers love their job teaching and that will be the main asset to become a professional teacher. Student success is greatly influenced by teacher performance, because teachers have an important role in educational efforts.

H₄ = There is a significant direct influence between Professional Commitment to Teacher Performance. The performance measurement process often requires statistical evidence to determine the level of progress of an organization in achieving its goals. The fundamental purpose behind taking measurements is to improve performance in general. Performance measurement is used as a basis for assessing the success and failure of implementation. Job satisfaction is a person's perspective, both positive and negative about their work (Siagian, 2014). Job satisfaction is the impact or result of the effectiveness of performance and success at work.

H₅ = There is a significant direct effect between Job Satisfaction and Teacher Performance. According to Supriyadi (1998) the term professionalism refers to the degree of individual appearance as a professional or the appearance of a job as a profession. Professionalism is directly proportional to performance and is also related to organizational commitment, so it is essential for a teacher to maintain and improve their professional abilities.

H₆ = Professional commitment has an indirect effect on teacher performance through organizational commitment. Organizational commitment as an initial sign of job satisfaction, and finds a significant positive relationship between Organizational Commitment and job satisfaction affects service quality in an effort to achieve company goals (Mathis & Jackson, 2011).

H₇ = Job satisfaction has an indirect effect on performance through organizational commitment.

2. Method

This research uses a quantitative approach. The quantitative approach emphasizes meaning, reasoning, the definition of a particular situation, examines more things related to everyday life. A qualitative approach, emphasizes the process compared to the final result, therefore the sequence of activities can vary depending on the conditions and the number of symptoms found. Research objectives are usually related to things that are practical. This study uses primary data which is data collected by researchers directly from its main source, this data collection uses a questionnaire given to school teachers as respondents, amounting to 29 school teachers.

2.1 Research Design

Figure 1. Research Framework

From figure above, the hypothesis 6 and 7 goes through Organizational Commitment, where in next segment of this study, will be calculated the indirect impact from both independent variables to dependent variable. Figure 1 also represent structural flow of the equation that will be divided further into two sub-structure.

2.2 Path Analysis

This analysis is used in examining the magnitude of the contribution shown by the path coefficient on each path diagram of the causal relationship between independent variables on moderation and its impact on the dependent variable. Path analysis is a technique for estimating the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable from a set of observed correlations, providing a pattern of causal relationships between variables. This path analysis technique will be used in testing the amount of contribution (contribution) shown by the path coefficient on each path diagram of the causal relationship between the independent variable on moderation and its impact on the dependent variable. Correlation and regression analysis which is the basis for calculating the path coefficient. There are three stages in conducting path analysis, namely formulating hypotheses and structural equations, calculating the path coefficient based on the regression coefficient, calculating the path coefficient individually.

3. Results

3.1 Sub-structure I Test

The sub-structure I test consists of Job Satisfaction and Professional Commitment as independent variable, and Organizational Commitment as dependent variable. Where the following are the results of data processing for sub-structure I testing.

Table 1. Model Summary of Sub-structure I

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	p-value	R-square
	beta	Std. Error	beta			
Constants	0,719	0,494		1,454	0,152	0,375
Job Satisfaction	0,400	0,119	0,389	3,346	0,001	
Professional Commitment	0,298	0,103	0,334	2,875	0,006	

From table 1 above it could be seen that Job Satisfaction and Professional Commitment, both have direct and significant impact to Organizational Commitment by their p-value of 0.001 and 0.006, respectively. Organizational Commitment is influenced by Job Satisfaction and Professional Commitment simultaneously by 38% based on the R-square value, and the remaining 62% is influenced by other factors. Every increase in Job Satisfaction by one point, it will influence Organizational Commitment by 0.400, and vice versa. Every increase in Professional Commitment by one point, it will also influence Organizational Commitment by 0.298, and vice versa.

Figure 2. Sub-structure I Framework

Figure 2 shows the complete structural framework for sub-structure I equation. It can be seen on figure 2 as Professional Commitment and Job Satisfaction have standardized coefficient of 0.334 and 0.389, respectively to Organizational Commitment. And path coefficient of 0.790 ($\sqrt{1-0.375}$). Therefore, the structural equation of sub-structure I testing is as follow:

$$Z = 0.334X_1 + 0.389X_2 + 0.790\varepsilon_1 \quad (1)$$

3.2 Sub-structure II Test

The second sub-structure test consists of Teacher Performance, Job Satisfaction, Professional Commitment, and Organizational Commitment. Where the following are the results of data processing for sub-structure II testing.

Table 2. Model Summary of Sub-structure II

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	p-value	R-square
	beta	Std. Error	beta			
Constants	1,327	0,313		4,233	0,000	0,560
Job Satisfaction	0,288	0,081	0,381	3,541	0,001	
Professional Commitment	0,196	0,069	0,299	2,844	0,006	
Organizational Commitment	0,177	0,082	0,240	2,142	0,037	

From table 2 above it can be seen that Job Satisfaction, Professional Commitment, and Organizational Commitment have direct and significant impact to Teacher Performance by their p-value of 0.001, 0.006, and 0,037 respectively. Teacher performance is influenced by three factors as follow, Job Satisfaction, Professional Commitment and Organizational Commitment simultaneously by 56% and the remaining 44% is influenced by other factors. Every increase in Job Satisfaction by one point, it will influence Teacher Performance by 0.288, and vice versa. For every increase in Professional Commitment by one point, it will influence Teacher Performance by 0.196, and vice versa. For each increase in Organizational Commitment by one point, it will influence Teacher Performance by 0.177, and vice versa.

Figure 3. Sub-structure II Framework

Figure 3 shows the complete structural framework for sub-structure II equation. It can be seen on figure 3 as Professional Commitment, Job Satisfaction, and Organizational Commitment have standardized coefficient of 0.299, 0.381, and 0.240, respectively to Teacher Performance. And path coefficient of 0.663 ($\sqrt{1-0.560}$). Therefore, the structural equation of sub-structure II testing is as follow:

$$Y = 0.299X_1 + 0.381X_2 + 0.240Z + 0.663\varepsilon_2 \quad (2)$$

3.3 Indirect Impact and Total Impact

If the two structural models are combined, there will be an indirect impact of 0.080 (0.334×0.240) and total impact of 0.379 ($0.299+0.080$) experienced by the Professional Commitment on Teacher Performance through Organizational Commitment. There is also an indirect impact of 0.093 (0.389×0.240) and total impact of 0.474 ($0.381+0.093$) experienced by the Job Satisfaction on Teacher Performance through Organizational Commitment.

4. Conclusion

Job Satisfaction has a significant effect on increasing Organizational Commitment, Professional Commitment has a significant effect on Organizational Commitment, Job Satisfaction has a significant effect on Teacher Performance, Professional Commitment has a significant effect on Teacher Performance. Organizational Commitment affects Teacher Performance, Job Satisfaction indirectly affects Teacher Performance through Organizational Commitment, and Professional Commitment indirectly affects Teacher Performance through Organizational commitment.

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